

ISic2710

I.Sicily inscription 2710

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Tonnarella

Provenance

contrada Prestopaolo, north of Messina/Palermo road, 700m from beach

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tonnarella

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645130

Bibliography

Calderone, S. 1949. *Analecta epigraphica liparenisia. Epigraphica*. 11: 49-60. At 59-60 ph

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